

THE
SICARIIDAE
OF
SOUTH
AFRICA

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THE SICARIIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Sicariidae contains three genera and 169 species. Two of the genera *Hexophthalma* and *Loxosceles* represented by 14 species, are known from South Africa. The Six eyed Sand Spiders (*Hexophthalma*) was revised by Lotz (2018) and four species are recognized from South Africa. Three of the species have a wide distribution and is listed as Least Concern with only *Hexophthalma leroyi* Lotz, 2018 that is Data Deficient. The Violin Spiders (*Loxosceles*) was revised by Lotz (2017) and 10 species are recognized from South Africa. Six of the species have a wide distribution and is listed as Least Concern and three are Data Deficient. Only the cave species *Loxosceles speluncarum* Simon, 1893 listed as Vulnerable under criterion D2 due to their decline in caves around Tshwane.

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Hexophthalma hahni male and female Photo Gordon Ackermann

FAMILY SICARIIDAE Keyserling, 1880

The family Sicariidae contains three genera and 169 species. Two of the genera *Hexophthalma* and *Loxosceles* represented by 14 species, are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: *Hexophthalma* (Six-eyed Sand Spiders); *Loxosceles* (Violin Spiders).

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL: 8-19 mm. Carapace in *Hexophthalma* relatively flat; wide as long; integument hard and covered with numerous short thick setae; in *Loxosceles* carapace longer than wide with conspicuous deeply impressed fovea; clypeus and chelicerae directed to the front; usually with “violin-shaped” darker marking on anterior part of carapace; six eyes arranged in three diads. Abdomen in *Hexaphthalma* roundish clothed with sickle-shaped setae arranged in patterns; in *Loxosceles* oval with numerous thin scattered setae. Legs in *Hexaphthalma* strong and clothed with numerous sickle-shaped setae; in *Loxosceles* the legs are longer and more slender.

LIFE STYLE: *Hexophthalma* is a free-living ground spider that has the ability to stay for long periods beneath the soil surface. With the help of their legs, sand is rapidly thrown over their bodies, this enable them to completely disappear beneath the surface. The tufts of sickle-shaped setae on their abdomen and legs help in holding the sand covering in place. Only during mating the males are more active and aggressive and roam around above ground in search of a mate. The egg cocoon is cup-like in shape and is buried in the sand.

Members of *Loxosceles* can be divided into two groups: the savanna or grassland species and the cave dwellers. The savanna species are found under rocks, logs, in old termite nests or in rubble. In *L. spinulosa* the gestation period is roughly three months and 3-4 egg cocoons are produced containing about 15 eggs each. Spiderlings reach maturity within a year and live at least 3 years.

TAXONOMY: The African Sicariidae has been treated by Newlands (1975, 1980, 1981), Lotz (2012, 2018) and Magalhães et al. (2017).

Hexophthalma sp. carapace Photo ASD

Sicarius sp. carapace Photo ASD

GENUS *HEXOPHTHALMA* Karsch, 1879

COMMON NAME: Six-eyed Sand Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Hexophthalma hahni* (Karsch, 1878)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL: male and female 8-11 mm. Colour of body and legs vary from light brown, reddish brown or dark brown or grey. Carapace about as wide as long, with one or multiple rows of macro-setae on lateral borders; dorsal macro-setae arranged in a central group surrounded by 4–5 pairs of macro-setae lines; six eyes arranged in three diads; anterior median eyes absent; labium longer than wide, tapering distally, partially fused to sternum; chelicerae fused at the base. Sternum wider than long; posteriorly truncate; with three outer rows of longer macro-setae near the border; shorter macro-setae in the middle. Abdomen rounded, slightly truncate posteriorly, with 3–6 paired transversal rows of macro-setae. Leg femora covered in the dorsal surface by macro-setae; tibia with eight rows of pointed macro-setae; tarsus without an onychium.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers that has the ability to stay for long periods beneath the soil surface.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Lotz (2012, 2018) and Magalhães et al. (2017).

NOTES: Species of *Hexophthalma* have raised interest because of their supposed medical importance (Newlands & Atkinson 1988; Van Aswegen et al. 1997). The venom of some of the species has even been considered as one of the strongest spider venoms (Newlands 1986), but this has never been proved (Lotz 2018).

Sicarius sp. female dorsal view Photo Peter Webb

Sicarius sp. female anterior view showing the eyes Photo Peter Webb

Hexophthalma albospinosa (Purcell, 1908)

COMMON NAME: Namibian Six-Eyed Sand Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Purcell (1908) as *Sicarius albospinosus* from Namibia. In South Africa recorded only from the Northern Cape (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 357 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in southern Africa, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers found beneath stones in sandy areas, buried in the sand. Sampled from the Desert Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Bloeddrift, West of Arnisfont, Richtersveld (-29.002, 17.099).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Lotz (2018) and Magalhães et al. (2017). Known from both sexes.

Palp and spermathecae after Magalhães et al. (2017)

Hexophthalma hahni (Karsch, 1878)

COMMON NAME: Hahn's Six-Eyed Sand Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Karsch (1878) as *Sicarius hahnii* from Namibia. Recorded from three southern African countries. In South Africa recorded from five provinces occurring in more than 10 protected areas (EEO=1 152 280 km²; AOO=228 km²; 14-1466 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Specimens are found beneath stones in sandy areas, buried in the sand at the entrances of animal burrows and at the base of rock overhangs or cliff faces. Sampled from the Desert, Grassland, Fynbos, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Klein Letaba (-23.13, 30.43); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Soutpansberg Farm Dorps Rivier 696 Farm Harnham (-22.36, 29.22); Louis Trichardt, 8 km W of Bluegumspoor road (-23.047, 29.904); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi 15 km SW (-23.17, 31.3); Kruger National Park, Pafuri area (-22.46, 31.3); Limpopo Valley National Park (-22.22, 29.13); Makgabeng area, W of Senwabawana (-23.24, 28.85); Rochdale, near Waterpoort (-22.54, 29.41); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43); Vhembe Biosphere Gonden Communal land (-22.914, 30.050). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg Farm Smutsfield 446 (-25.09, 30.46); Bango Poort, Cave Poort (-24.58, 31.1). **North West:** Groot Marico (-25.6, 26.43); Strydpoort Hoogenoeg, Strydpoort Mts. (-26.99, 25.97); Zeerust (-25.53, 26.08). **Northern Cape:** Gordonia (-28.7, 20.96); Louisvale (-28.58, 21.2); Naroep (-28.98, 18.58): 127.4 km W Pofadder (-29.129, 19.395); 45 km S of Vioolsdrift (-29.108, 17.846); Kenhardt, towards Upington (-29.35, 21.15); Springbok (-29.667, 17.883); Twee Rivieren, Kalahari Gemsbok National Park (-26.472, 20.612); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Blackridge, E of Langberge, E-NE of Groblershoop (-28.49, 22.32); Bushmanland, Krapohl Island (-28.11, 32.29); Calvinia, Klein Arendskraal (-31.46, 19.77); Douglas (-29.05, 23.77); Eselsfontein, south of Grootdrink (-28.62, 21.68); Kamieskroon (-30.20, 17.93); Namaqualand, Kap Kap 382 (-30.16, 18.22); Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve (-31.45, 19.1); Koingnaas (-30.57, 17.57);

Palp and spermathecae after Newlands (1986).

Hexophthalma hahni from Tswalu GR Photo P. Webb

Hexophthalma hahni (continued)

Rooipoort Nature Reserve Site 1 (-28.561, 24.162); Namaqua National Park (-30.05, 17.35); Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Carnarvon (-30.97, 22.12); 68.6 km S of Britstown (-30.58, 23.5); Victoria West(-31.40, 23.12. **Western Cape:** Bitterfontein 46 km E of Bitterfontein (-31.03, 18.26); Clanwilliam, Sanddrif Dwarsrivier 330 (-32.47, 19.27); Doringbaai (-31.81, 18.24); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof (-33.36, 21.69); Hans Strydom Dam Nature Reserve, Mogol (-33.95, 22.46); The Island, S of Herbertsdale (-34.01, 21.76); 19 km SE of Klaver (-31.76, 18.62); Lutzville, Vlêrmuisklip, near Vredendal (-31.54, 18.35); Pappendorp, near Olifants River Estuary (-31.81, 18.24); Vanrhynsdorp, Van Rhyn's Pass (-31.6, 18.75); Gordon's Bay (-34.16, 18.87); Piketberg (-32.90, 18.75); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Ladismith(-33.5, 21.26); Cederberg Wilderness Area 5.4, 664 masl. (-32.4, 19.09). Donkin's Bay (-31.56, 18.16); Cederberg Wilderness Area.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no threats known. It is protected in several protected areas such as Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999), Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018), Namaqua National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005), Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016) and Kalahari Gemsbok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Lotz (2012, 2018) and synonymized with *Hexaphthalma testaceus*. Known from both sexes. *Sicarius oweni* Newlands, 1986: 53 is an unpublished synonym of *H. hahni*.

Hexophthalma hahni Photo Les Oates

Hexophthalma hahni female with the help of her legs, sand are rapidly thrown over her body, to enable her to completely disappear beneath the surface. Photo Les Oates

Hexophthalma leroyi Lotz, 2018

COMMON NAME: Leroy's Six-Eyed Sand Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Lotz (2018) and known only from the type locality Augrabies National Park (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 635 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dweller, collected in a grassy area in the Nama Karoo Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Species presently protected in the Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female (Lotz 2018).

Spermathecae after Lotz (2018)

Hexophthalma spatulatus (Pocock, 1900)

COMMON NAME: Six-Eyed Sand Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONAL: A South African endemic described in 1900 as *Sicarius spatulatus* from Port Elizabeth. The species is presently known from two provinces and it is protected in De Hoop Nature Reserve and Kammanasie Nature Reserve (EOO=84 710 km²; AOO=60 km²; 4-756 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Western Cape:** Borrelfontein, 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.33, 21.85); Gouritsmond, 8 km W (-34.34, 21.87); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Bredasdorp (-34.53, 20.04); Caledon (-32.4, 19.43); Piketberg (-32.90, 18.75S); Swellendam, Tradouws Pass (-33.95, 20.7); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Koppie Alleen cottage (-34.286, 20.286); Van der Kemps Kloof (-33.876, 25.454); Kammanasie Nature Reserve (-33.66, 23.12); N of Mosselbay (-34.010, 22.056).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no threat known. Species protected in Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Kammanasie Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Lotz (2012, 2018) and Magalhaes et al. (2017). Known from both sexes.

Hexophthalma spatulatus
(Pocock, 1900)

Palp after Magalhaes et al. (2017).

Palp and eye pattern Photo ASD

Hexophthalma spatulatus female from Addo NP
Photo ASD

Hexophthalma spatulatus female from Addo NP
Photo Linda Wiese

GENUS *LOXOSCELES* Heinecken & Lowe 1835

COMMON NAME: Violin Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Loxosceles rufescens* (Dufour, 1820)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL: female 5-15 mm; male 3.5-12 mm. Colour of body is yellowish to reddish brown with contrasting darker markings; legs and palpi light brown. Carapace slightly longer than wide with conspicuous deeply impressed fovea; clypeus and chelicerae directed to the front; usually with “violin shaped” darker marking on anterior part of carapace; six eyes arranged in a recurved row in 3 groups each with 2 eyes; anterior median eyes absent; labium longer than wide, tapering distally, partially fused to sternum; chelicerae fused at the base. Abdomen oval; light brown usually with dark patterns. Leg long and slender with two claws.

LIFESTYLE: They can be divided into two groups: the savanna or grassland species and the cave dwellers. The grassland species are found under rocks, logs, and bark of trees, in old termite nests or in rubble and are sampled from the Grassland, Savanna, Nama- and Succulent- Karoo. They are not retreat bound and they spin only a few irregular strands of silk serving as retreats under objects on the ground. In buildings they are found in dark corners. The gestation period is roughly three months and 3-4 egg cocoons are produced, containing about 15 eggs sacs. Spiderlings reach maturity within a year and live at least three years (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle 2014). The *Loxosceles* species (*L. makapanensis*, *L. parramae* and *L. spelucarum*) are cave dwellers and more commonly found in the total dark zone than in the twilight zone (Lawrence 1964; Newlands 1986; Nelson et al. 2003; Marais & Durand 2006; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Myburg 2009).

TAXONOMY: Revised by Lotz (2012, 2018) and Magalhães et al. (2017).

NOTES: Species of *Loxosceles* have raised interest because of their medical importance. (Newlands & Atkinson 1988; Müller et al. 2012). They produce a cytotoxic venom that destroys the tissue around the bite site. The bite is painless, apparently superficial, and initially goes unnoticed. About two hours after the bite a red swollen lesion, sometimes with a purple centre, starts to develop.

Loxosceles simillima female Photo J. Leeming

Loxosceles simillima female with egg sac Photo Leon Lotz

Loxosceles cederbergensis Lotz, 2017

COMMON NAME: Cederberg Violin Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Lotz (2017) from Aan Het Berg in the Cederberg Wilderness Area. The species was sampled from different localities in the Cederberg (EOO=324 km²; AOO=24 km²; 243-1523 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers that were sampled with pitfall traps in the Cederberg Wilderness Area in the Fynbos Biome. The species was mainly sampled between 92 m a.s.l. to 1660 m a.s.l.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg 257 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneeuokop, 1660 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.15); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Niewoudt's Pass, 551 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Crystal Pools, Wupperthal, 92 m a.s.l. (-32.31, 19.18); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sawadee, 359 m a.s.l. (-32.34, 18.99); Cederberg Wilderness Area 664 m a.s.l. (-32.4, 19.09).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Although protected in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016) more sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

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Spermathecae after Lotz (2017)

Loxosceles cederbergensis from Cederberg SANSVA VM

Loxosceles dejagerae Lotz, 2017

COMMON NAME: Marie's Violin Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lotz (2017) from the Swartberg Nature Reserve (listed as Gamkaskloof Nature Reserve). The species is known from three provinces and protected at the type locality (EOO=34 540 km²; AOO=20 km²; 55-1287 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore, listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller sampled from the Fynbos and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Willowmore (-33.30 23.50). **Northern Cape:** Victoria West, Biesjiesfontein (-31.40, 23.12). **Western Cape:** Prince Albert, Swartberg Pass (-33.31, 22.05); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof (-33.3415, 21.8768).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There is no significant threats. Species protected in the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Loxosceles dejagerae from Middelburg Photo M. de Jager

Palp and spermathecae after Lotz (2017)

***Loxosceles haddadi* Lotz, 2017**

COMMON NAME: Haddad's Violin Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described by Lotz (2017) from Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (was Lajuma) (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1341 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller collected from under rocks in the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Species protected in the Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male.

Loxosceles makapanensis Lotz, 2017

COMMON NAME: Makapan Violin Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described by Lotz (2017) from the Ficus Cave in Makapan Valley, (EOO=8 km²; AOO=8 km²; 1404-1911 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure it is known only from two localities in Makapan Valley. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller collected from caves in the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

.DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Makapan Valley Ficus Cave (-24.07, 29.25); Mike's Cave (-24.1167, 29.2333).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats but more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Loxosceles parramae Newlands, 1981

COMMON NAME: Parram's Violin Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Newlands (1981) from Bellevue, Johannesburg in Gauteng. The species is known from two provinces including three protected areas: (EOO=80 931 km²; AOO=104 km²; 1194-2158 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

LIFESTYLE: *Loxosceles parrami* was artificially introduced in human homes and mines in South Africa and is found in cracks and crevices in stone foundations or in houses where it takes refuge in dark corners of cupboards and drawers (Newlands, 1980). Collected from the Grassland Biome found under rocks and in caves and buildings.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Free State: Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65); Bloemfontein Dan Pienaar (-29.11, 26.22); Fouriesburg, Tepelkop 323 (-28.45, 28.08); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Wyndford Guest Farm, Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24); Qwa-Qwa Mountain (-28.5, 28.77); Harrismith (-28.27, 29.13); Reitz (-27.79, 28.44); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13); Fouriesburg, Old Mill Mountain Resort (-28.36, 28.28). **Gauteng:** Benoni (-26.19, 28.31); Boksburg (-26.13, 28.15); Germiston (-26.21, 28.15); Auckland Park (-26.20, 28.04); Bryanston (-26.06, 28.05); Crown Mines (-26.12, 28.05); Illovo (-26.7, 28.3); Parktown (-26.18, 28.03); Yeoville (-26.18, 28.07); Kensington (-26.19, 28.11); Walkerville (-26.4, 27.96); Kenilworth (-28.69, 24.8); Walkerville (-26.4, 27.96); Rosebank, Johannesburg (-26.145, 28.041); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.20); Apies River Cave, Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.7833, 28.2167).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Species protected in the Amanzi Private Game Reserve, Mpetsane Conservation Estate and Groenkloof Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Species revised by Lotz (2012, 2017). Known from both sexes.

Loxosceles parramae from Wyndford Farm Photo P. Webb

Loxosceles parramae from Kempton Park Photo W. Schmidt

Palp and spermathecae after Newlands (1981)

Loxosceles pilosa Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Steinkopf Violin Spider

NATIONAL STATUS : LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Steinkopf in the Northern Cape. Known also from Namibia. In South Africa recorded only from Northern Cape (EEO=12 015 km²; AOO=16 km²; 63-870 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in southern Africa, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Specimens are commonly found beneath small stones on sandy loam soils in the Desert and Nama Karoo biomes (Newlands 1986). It has also been found at several localities in the dunes where it hides amongst grass clusters during the day.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Little Namaqualand, Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Sendelingsdrif (-28.13, 16.90); Coboop (Bontduine) dunes, Onseepkans (-28.75, 19.35); Kakamas (-28.76, 20.61).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Lotz (2012, 2017). Known from both sexes.

Palp and spermathecae after Lotz (2017)

Loxosceles rufescens (Dufour, 1820)

COMMON NAME: Mediterranean Recluse Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species that was introduced into South Africa in 1914 where it was sampled from a building in Cape Town (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 7 m a.s.l.). No additional specimens were sampled. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Only a single specimen recorded from South Africa from building in 1914 in Cape Town. Accidental introduction.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Southern Europe, northern Africa to Iran. Introduced to USA, Mexico, Macaronesia, South Africa, India, China, Japan, Korea, Laos, Thailand, Australia, Hawaii.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Species since 1914 not resampled. Known from both sexes.

Palp

Loxosceles simillima Lawrence, 1927

COMMON NAME: Northern Violin Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1927) from Namibia. Known from nine African countries. In South Africa recorded from six provinces and occurring in more than 14 protected areas (EOO=475 660 km²; AOO=312 km²; 83-1816 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers. They are not web bound and they spin only a few irregular strands of silk serving as retreats. Collected from under rocks, logs and bark and from inside termite mounds, leaf litter, caves and buildings. Sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Botswana, DRC, Mozambique, Namibia, Zambia Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.13, 26.17); Langenhovenpark Bloemfontein (-29.133, 26.166); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68) Fouriesburg Farm Moodiam (-28.61, 28.23); Petrusburg Sterkfontein farm (-29.18, 25.28); Sterkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-28.48, 29.01); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.59, 25.45); Stowlands Farm Boshof (-27.90, 25.20). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01); iSimangaliso Wetland park Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.5444, 32.1546); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.034, 32.425). **Limpopo:** Acacia Lodge Game Reserve Thabazimbi (-24.3834, 27.7185); Amsterdam Farm Dendron (-23.3667, 29.3167); Dwarsrivier 56km S of Louis Trichardt (-23.5167, 29.7167); Bergpan Soutpansberg (-23.39, 30.94); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Blouberg NR North BLN01 Vhembi Biosphere (-22.988, 29.127); Blouberg NR North BLN05 Vhembi Biosphere (-22.963, 29.103); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Kruger National Park 5 km N of Letaba Camp (-22.93, 31.02); Kruger National Park Bateleur Bushveld Camp (-23.2342, 31.2022); Kruger National Park Letaba Rest Camp (-23.851, 31.577); Kruger National Park Pafuri (-22.46, 31.30); Wallers Camp/Pafuri River Camp (-22.4237, 30.9108); Lhuvhondo Nature reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Naboomspruit Farm London (-24.5, 28.72); Mussina (-22.33, 30.03); Rochdale Farm (-22.54, 29.41); Pietersburg (-23.89, 29.46); Venetia Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.320, 29.324); Vhembi Biosphere Barries Farm BAR06 (-22.478, 29.405); Vhembi Biosphere Bristow Farm BRI 6 (-23.166, 29.776); Vhembi Biosphere Gonden Communal land GON3 (-22.914, 30.050); Vhembi Biosphere Gonden Communal

Loxosceles simillima Photo P. Webb

Carapace Photo ASD

Male palp Photo ASD

Palp and spermathecae after Lotz (2017)

Loxosceles simillima Lawrence, 1927

land GON7(-22.905, 29.995); Vhembi Biosphere Ludwig's Lust Farm LUD08 (-22.223, 29.801); Vhembi Biosphere Mara Research Station MAA04 (-23.132, 29.548); Vhembi Biosphere Mara Research Station MAA08 (-23.118, 29.546); Vhembi Biosphere Nwanedi Game Res. NWA 5(-22.634, 30.400); Vhembi Biosphere Nwanedi Game Res. NWA 7 (-22.634, 30.387); Thabazimbi (-24.60, 27.38); Lephallale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Kruger National Park Letaba (-23.83, 31.58); Kruger National Park Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Kruger National Park Shingwedzi 15 km SW (-23.17, 31.3); Kruger National Park Shingwedzi 20 km N(-22.9, 31.37); Kruger National Park Silvervis Dam (-24.01, 31.48); Beit Bridge 14km W of Beit Bridge (-22.0667, 29.8333); Leopard Creek NR (-23.50, 27.57); Londolozi (-24.30,31.32); Driefontein (-24.26, 28.45); Leeudorings (-24.53, 28.18); Tuinplaas (-24.54, 28.44).

Mpumalanga: Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Kruger National Park: Lwakahle (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park Makhuthwanini 04 (-25.38, 31.6); Kruger National Park Satara 07(-25.38, 32.13); Kruger National Park Skukuza (-25.00, 31.97); Kruger National Park Sabiepoort 11 (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park Vutome 06 (-25.24, 32.08); Kruger National Park Vutomi 09 (-24.61, 31.79); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58); Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33); Vaalfontein (-25.10, 29.24); Althorpe (-25.32, 31.20); Marble Hall (-24.58, 29.18). **North West:** Potchefstroom (-26.70, 27.09); Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Klerksdorp (-26.84, 26.67); Zeerust (-25.53, 26.08). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley, Secretarius 89 (-28.67, 24.48); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.30, 22.45); Herbert, Douglas (-29.05, 23.77); Herbert, Geelkoppies (-28.44, 23.53); Herbert, Mushavi G. Ranch (-28.53, 23.55); Kimberley (-28.44, 24.46); Kimberley, Rivierplaas (-29.02,24.40).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in more than 14 protected areas).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Lotz (2012, 2018) and synonymized with *Loxosceles spiniceps* Lawrence, 1952. Known from both sexes.

Loxosceles simillima from Tswalu Game Reserve Photo P. Webb

Loxosceles speluncarum Simon, 1893

COMMON NAME: Gauteng Cave Violin Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: VU National Criteria D2

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Gauteng endemic described by Simon (1893) from Fountain Caves, Pretoria (EOO=315 km²; AOO=20 km²; 1262-1498 m a.s.l.). Known from only fewer than three extant locations this species is potentially threatened by disturbance of its specialist cave habitat. Therefore, listed as Vulnerable under criterion D2.

LIFESTYLE: *Loxosceles speluncarum* is known only from three cave complexes in the Pretoria area. It is a troglobite cave species that are more abundant in totally dark areas where they have been recorded from crevices or wandering around on the cave walls.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Gauteng: Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.2); Pretoria/Tshwane, Apies River Cave (-25.68, 28.21); Pretoria/ Tshwane, Fountain Caves (-25.79, 28.22); Pretoria/ Tshwane, Monument Park Caves (-25.80, 28.23); Pretoria/ Tshwane, Wonderboom Caves (-25.65, 28.65).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is known from several caves around Pretoria including caves in the Groenkloof Nature Reserve. Surveys about twenty years after the first recordings, showed that this species has completely disappeared from two of the caves (Apies River Caves and Monument Caves) and is under severe threat of disappearing from the third cave (Wonderboom Caves). The third cave is in the Wonderboom Nature Reserve and the population is protected and seems to be safe for the immediate future (Newlands 1975; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Myburg 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Lotz (2012, 2017). Known from both sexes.

Palp and spermatheca after Lotz (2017)

Loxosceles speluncarum female Photo Jarrod Todd

Loxosceles spinulosa Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Southern Violin Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Swellendam Pass in the Western Cape. In South Africa recorded only from two southern provinces including four protected areas (EOO=45 341 km²; AOO=40 km²; 15-987 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They are not web bound and they spin only a few irregular strands of silk serving as retreats. Sampled from the Fynbos and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffreys Bay.(-34.05, 24.92); Great Fish River Reserve, Ulster farm border (-33.4833, 27.1333); Hankey, Bavianskloof Rd. (-33.83, 24.88). **Western Cape:** Avontuur Pass (-33.72, 23.16); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Potberg (-34.2248, 20.3198); Heidelberg, Grootvadersbos Nature Reserve (-33.9784, 20.8109); Meiringspoort (-33.4, 22.55); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof (-33.36, 21.69); Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.494, 21.088).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009), Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005), Great Fish River Reserve and Aardvark Nature Reserve

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Lotz (2012, 2017). Known from both sexes.

Loxosceles spinulosa male from Aardvark NR Photo P. Webb

Loxosceles spinulosa male from Aardvark NR Photo P. Webb

Loxosceles spinulosa male from Montagu Photo W. Juber

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Palp and spermathecae after Lotz (2017)

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